

**PERCEIVED EFFECT OF LISTENING TO MUSIC TOWARDS
STUDY HABIT OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN MINDANAO
STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU**

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ABSTRACT

Listening to music toward study habits has become a usual practice of most students. Generally, music plays a vital part when studying and it affects the students regarding their academic performance either negatively or positively. The purpose of this study is to answer the question: What is the perceived effect of listening to music toward study habits? The study determined the perceived effect of listening to music and how is it connected to study habits of the students, particularly the grade 11 students. This research was conducted in Mindanao State University – Sulu, Senior High School on the second semester academic year 2024 - 2025. The researchers utilized using the quantitative research under the method of descriptive correlation design to describe the characteristics, average, and trends of the respondents. The researchers used the 25% each of the total population of GAS and STEM strand of the grade 11 student where they were assessed by a conducted survey question. A survey method was used to evaluate the results for the study in a form of questionnaires. There were one hundred (100) respondents that has been randomly selected out of the total population of the grade 11 students and majority of the respondents agreed to the perceived effect of listening to music toward study habits. This means that the respondents are affected by the effect of listening to music toward study habits. However, there is no significant relationship between the two variables which are the: effect of listening to music and study habits, when categorized according to gender and strand. Therefore, listening to music is not bad at all. It is helpful to some students while studying their lesson. The researchers recommended to the readers, students, teachers that listening to music while studying, they just need to limit their time and exposure to music while studying.

Keywords: *Listening to Music, Perceived Effect, Study Habits, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Listening to music while studying became a usual practice in the student's population. This pattern raises concerns. How can music affect one's concentration and performance when studying, according to Dolegui (2013), there is a well-known expression The term 'The Mozart effect' was coined to describe how listening to classical music, such as Mozart, can aid boost intelligence. IQ in spatial reasoning. Even in today's time, listening to music whilst studying and completing assignments appear to be a worldwide phenomenon.

According to Pollard & Courage (2017), it is further suggested that students who can realistically gauge their multitasking skill will perform better across different multitasking activities. In addition, music is one of the great important things in the students.

Regardless of the student's perception towards the effect of listening to music among the Grade 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School, evaluating the effects of listening to music towards study habits is essential for further analyzation if the music influences the students' study habits or not. Hence, listening to informational music serves as a way of learning for others and learning is an important aspect in education as uttered by Sabbaha et. al., (2024) cited by Jailani et. al., (2024) Abdulmajid et. al., (2024), Balla et. al., (2024) Jarak et. al., (2024), Sabbaha et. al., (2024), Sasapan et. al., (2024), Sabbaha et. al., (2024), Basir et. al., (2024) and Sakili et. al., (2024) With this, the researchers provided these statements; The demographic profile of the students according to gender and strand, the effects of listening to music towards study habits, and the significant differences between listening to music and study habits when categorized according to gender and strand.

Based on the researcher's initial review of related literature and considering the specific context, it has been observed that there is a lack of research on the topic Perceive Effect of Listening to Music Towards Study Habits. While there is existing literature on the perception of listening to music towards study habits, in various educational settings, there is a need to investigate its prevalence, impact, and unique factors specifically among senior high school students. The researcher may have learned from experience or through literature review that perception on listening to music while studying can have detrimental effects on students' academic performance, concentration, and overall well-being However, no study has been conducted to explore the specific manifestation. Addressing these perceptions and its research gap will provide valuable insights into the experiences of these students and contribute to the development of targeted interventions and support systems to alleviate studying with music and enhance students' ability on their cognitive performance.

Research Questions

The researchers were able to seek out the effects of listening to music towards study habits of the selected 100 Grade 11 students of both STEM and GAS strands of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School.

With this, the researchers provided the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the students according to gender and strand?
2. What are the effects of listening to music towards study habits?
3. Is there a significant difference between listening to music and study habits when categorized according to gender and strand?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Mindanao State University-Sulu specifically at Senior High School Department among grade 11 students of STEM and GAS strand where they were assessed by conducting survey questions. The Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School is located at Capitol Site, Patikul, Sulu. The study was conducted in the second semester of the academic year 2024-2025.

Sampling Method

The researcher used 25% each of the total population from GAS and STEM strand grade 11 students at Mindanao State University - Sulu Senior High School. Only 100 samples were used in the study. The researcher then used the stratified random sampling technique to determine the quantity of samples for each selected section.

Research Instrument

A questionnaire was used as the study's instrument. The questionnaire and data were gathered by conducting a survey. A survey method was used to evaluate the results for the study. The researchers choose questionnaire in a form of survey to assisted them in determining as well as evaluating the perceptions of 11th grade learners both from GAS and STEM strand of Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School regarding the perceive effect of listening to music towards study habit. The questionnaire was divided into three parts, the first part deals with respondent's demographic profile which includes their name, gender, strand, & section. The second part deals with the corresponding queries on Female and Male actors that evaluate their perception regarding the effect of listening to music toward study habit. Lastly, the third part consists of the differences between listening to music and study habits according to the genders of the respondents.

The main component of surveys is questionnaires/ checklists. These are lists of questions/statements to collect data from a large group. In survey research, the questions are primarily closed-ended or include rating scales to collect data in a unified fashion.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After data collection, the data was analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, such as frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Inferential statistics, such as t-tests or regression analysis, were used to examine relationships between variables and test hypotheses.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research instrument will be approved by the members of the panel. Once approved, the researchers will prepare a formal letter to the SHS director for his approval in the conduct of the survey, consequently, the questionnaire will then be reproduced and will be distributed to the research respondents respectively and will be retrieved immediately after they finish answering.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this research are presented coherently to facilitate a clear understanding of the findings. The data collected from students in Mindanao State University-Sulu provide insights to the Perceive Effect of Listening to Music Towards Study Habits of Grade 11 Students.

Table 1.1

Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
MALE	48	48%
FEMALE	52	52%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 1.1 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of values in terms of gender. As shown in the table 48% of the respondents are males and 52% are females. This means that majority of the respondents are females.

Table 1.2

Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage
STEM	50	50%
GAS	50	50%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 1.2 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of values in terms of strand. The survey questionnaire was distributed equally to both strands. As shown in the table the STEM and GAS strand contains 50% each of the 100% respondents.

Table 2*Effect of Listening to Music Towards Study Habits*

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
1.Listening to music helps me feel relaxed.	1.7	.7	Strongly Agree
2. Listening to music helps me be energized.	1.8	.7	Agree
3. Listening to music helps me keep awake while studying.	2.0	.8	Agree
4.Listening to music motivates me while doing my assignments.	2.0	.8	Agree
5.Listening to music brings nothing but best ideas.	2.0	.7	Agree
6.Listening to music encourages me to finish my school task smoothly.	2.0	.8	Agree
7.Listening to music helps a lot in terms of retention.	2.1	.7	Agree
8.Listening to music keeps new information or innovates ideas.	2.1	.8	Agree
9.Listening to music boost my memorization skills.	2.3	.8	Agree
10.Listening to music helps me focus on the subject matter.	2.5	2.1	Disagree
GRAND MEAN	2.05	8.9	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75=SA;1.76-2.50=A;2.51-3.25=D;3.26-4.00=SD

Table 2 illustrates the effect of listening to music towards study habits of the students. The grand mean obtained 2.05 with the verbal description of Agree. This implies that listening to music is a positive effect to the students learning.

As shown in the table, the statement one obtained 1.7 with the verbal description of Strongly Agree. Which means that listening to music helps them feel relaxed while they're studying, and from statement number two until nine obtained a mean that falls under the verbal description of Agree ,which means the respondents agreed that listening to music helps them feel energized, keep them awake while studying, motivates them while doing their assignments, brings best ideas, encourages them toto finish their school task smoothly, helps in terms of retention, innovates new ideas, and boost their memorization skills. However, the statement ten obtained 2.5 with the verbal description of Disagree, which means that listening to music doesn't help them focus on the subject matter. But overall, the total of the verbal description is agreed. Which means that the students of Grade 11 both in STEM and GAS strand agreed to the effect of listening to music towards study habits. And it indicates that listening to music has a satisfaction to

the study habits of Grade 11 STEM and GAS strand.

This finding is related to the study of Pollard and Courage (2019) some other techniques that this study methodology agreed to the impact of listening to music on cognitive tests, they found out that listening to music has positive impact to the study habits of the students.

Table 3.1

Significant Difference Between Listening to Music and Study Habits when categorized according to Gender

Variable	Male		Female		t	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Gender	2.1	0.7	2.0	0.5	.350	.730

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

Table 3.1. A t-test or independent sample was performed to determine the significant difference of the two variables and as shown in the table the findings showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of Male (2.0750) and Female (2.0327) respondents; $t (.350) = 98$, the calculated P-value resulted. 730 which is higher above than the original P-value of 0.05 which means that there is no significant difference between the two variables when categorized according to gender and the null hypothesis is accepted which implies that there is no significant difference on the effect of listening to music towards study habits when categorized according to gender (Male and Female).

This study is related to the study of Alley & Greene 2008, Cauchard et al (2012) that tests under specific conditions had a greater effect on female participants who frequently listen to music when studying. It was conducted under subsequent conditions and nowadays, music is a constant and easily available alternative in daily life, particularly because it has the power to affect our feelings and emotions.

Table 3.2

Significant Difference Between Listening to Music and Study Habits when categorized according to Strand

Variable	STEM		GAS		t	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Strand	2.0	0.7	2.1	0.5	.350	.730

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

Table 3.2 illustrates the significant relationship between the two variables; Effect of Listening to Music (Independent Variable) and Study Habits (Dependent Variable) when categorized according to strand. A T-test or independent sample was performed to determine the significant difference of the two variables and as shown in the table the findings showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the strands; STEM (2.0200) and GAS (2.0860) ; $t (.350) = 98$, the calculated P-value resulted. 730 which is higher above than the original P-value of 0.05 which means that there is no significant relationship between the two variables when categorized according to strand and the null hypothesis is accepted which implies that there is no significant difference on

the effect of listening to music towards study habits when categorized according to strand (STEM and GAS).

Conclusions

This study was conducted, and the result reveals the following findings that imply significant effect to the beneficiaries of this study. The demographic profile of the student's gained 48% of the respondents are males and 52% are females and the survey questionnaires distributed equally to both STEM and GAS strand that contains 50% each of the 100% respondents.

Majority of the respondents resulted agree to the effect of listening to music towards study habits that obtained the grand mean of 2.05. This indicates that listening to music had been proven a positive effect to the respondents.

However, the two variables signify that there is no significant difference between listening to music and study habits when categorized by gender and strands when it comes to their perception about listening to music toward study habits based on the result.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the followings are recommended:

1. For the School Administration: Since the respondents agreed that listening to music is effective. It was recommended to the school administrator to have speakers on the library, it would be helpful to the students to be energized and relaxed when doing their schoolwork.
2. For the teacher: Due to the positive effect of the music based on the study, it was recommended to the teachers to play soft music while conducting quizzes and exams.
3. For the students: Since listening to music while studying claimed to be effective based on the study, it was recommended to the students to play music while studying to help them stay awake and energized when studying.
4. For the future researchers: It was recommended to conduct a study and examine the significant differences between the integration of music in classroom activities and no music at all.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Research ethics is a set of principles and guidelines that ensure the protection of human subjects in research studies. It is essential to consider ethical issues when conducting research, as the well-being of participants is of paramount importance. In this research study, the focus is on the effects of listening to music on the study habits of Grade 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School.

The following are some of the ethical considerations that should be considered

when designing and conducting this research:

1. **Voluntary participation:** Participation in the study should be voluntary, and participants should have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.
2. **Informed consent:** Participants should be informed about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and any potential risks or discomforts. They should also be given the opportunity to ask questions and express concerns.
3. **Confidentiality:** All personal information collected during the study should be kept confidential. This includes names, addresses, and any other identifying information.
4. **Privacy:** Participants should have their privacy respected during the study. This includes not being observed without their consent and having their personal space respected.
5. **Anonymity:** Whenever possible, participants should remain anonymous in the study. This means that their identities should not be linked to their data.
6. **Beneficence:** The research should be conducted in a way that is beneficial to the participants. This includes providing them with any necessary information, support, or resources.

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